

1 Supplementary Material 1 (S1)

2
 3 Figure 1. i) Photograph of incubation bottles; ii) sketch of treatments and Fe addition in the form
 4 of goethite: Fe; no Fe: nFe; medium Fe (4.4 mg g^{-1} , the weight of Fe): mFe; high Fe (44.6 mg g^{-1} , the
 5 weight of Fe): hFe; addition of phosphate is indicated by P; addition of silicic acid by Si.
 6 Red boxes mark the controls for each grouped treatment.

- 7 Green box and arrows show the grouped treatment A as the control for other treatment groups
- 8 with different levels of Fe (B, C, and D).

9 **Supplementary Material (S2)**

10 **Methods: analysis of gaseous samples**

11 The potential of CO₂ and CH₄ productions rates were measured to quantify microbial respiratory
12 activity during the course of the experiment. The concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄ in the incubation
13 bottles were measured over time using a gas chromatograph (SRI Instrument 8610C, Torrance,
14 USA) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and methanizer to simultaneously measure
15 CO₂ and CH₄. Before each sampling, the pressure inside the incubation bottles was measured
16 with a pressure sensor (GMH 3110, Greisinger, Regenstauf, Germany). The headspace of
17 incubation bottles was sampled using syringes, and samples were injected into the GC directly.
18 Concentrations were obtained by analyzing the headspace at the beginning (t₀:24 h) and after 72,
19 168 and 336 h (t₁ – t₃). The measured concentrations (in ppmV) were corrected for pressure and
20 converted using the ideal gas law:

$$21 \quad n = (p \cdot V) / (R \cdot T) \quad (1)$$

22 where n is the amount of substance in mol, p is the partial pressure in atm, V is the headspace
23 volume in L, R is the ideal gas constant (0.082 L atm mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) and T is the laboratory temperature
24 in K.

25 Total concentration of CO₂ and CH₄ in gas and water phase in the incubation bottles were
26 calculated using the ideal gas with constants corrected for 20 °C (K_H, CO₂= 3.8×10⁻² mol L⁻¹ atm⁻¹
27 and K_H, CH₄= 3.8×10⁻² mol L⁻¹ atm⁻¹, from Sander. R [1].

28

29 **Results and discussion:**

30 *Redox conditions and production of CO₂ and CH₄*

31 Under oxic conditions, microbial respiration is dominated by the reduction of molecular O₂ due
32 to its abundance and thermodynamic favorability as an electron acceptor, while anaerobic
33 respiration pathways using alternative terminal electron acceptors (TEAs) such as Fe(III), sulfate
34 or organic matter (OM) are suppressed until depletion of O₂. Thereafter, respiration using other
35 TEAs sets in, according to their thermodynamic energy yields [2]. The reduction of O₂ or
36 alternative TEAs through microbial respiration can be quantified by monitoring CO₂ production
37 from oxidation of labile OM [3]. Upon depletion of TEAs, reduction of CO₂ via hydrogenotrophic
38 methanogenesis or cleavage of acetate via acetoclastic methanogenesis leads to an equal
39 production of CH₄ and CO₂ under strictly methanogenic conditions [4].

40 As shown in the [Figure 2 S2](#) below, under anoxic conditions as established in our
41 incubations, high rates of anaerobic CO₂ production were indicative of active microbial
42 respiration and the onset of increasingly reducing conditions over a timescale of hours ([Figure 1,](#)
43 [a-c](#)). The availability of other TEAs, in our incubations mainly Fe(III) but presumably also OM
44 [5], leads to the retardation of CH₄ production. Accordingly, in the system with the higher Fe
45 content (hFe), the production of CH₄ is retarded longer and overall lower than in the nFe and mFe
46 systems ([Figure 1, d-f](#)). Thus, the production of CO₂ and onset of CH₄ production served as a good
47 indicator for redox conditions.

48

49

50 Figure 2. The rate of CO₂ (a–c) and CH₄ production (d–f) versus time during incubation under
 51 anoxic conditions. Data represent the mean; whiskers represent the standard deviation (n=3).
 52 Addition of goethite is indicated by Fe, where no Fe: nFe; medium Fe (4.4 mg g⁻¹): mFe; high Fe
 53 (44.6 mg g⁻¹): hFe; addition of phosphate is indicated by P; addition of silicic acid indicated by Si.

54

55 Table 1 Arsenite (As(III)) release rate (in % of total As in the system) during the course of the
 56 experiment. See methods section for analytical methods.

Treatments	Time			
	24	72	168	336
Fe Conc.– treatments				
nFe-C	21.5	80.0	68.0	51.0
nFe-P	6.0	33.0	63.0	35.0
nFe-Si	11.0	60.0	55.0	61.0
nFe-Si+P	15.2	46.4	52.0	61.3
mFe-C	28.0	80.0	73.0	67.0
mFe-P	12.2	62.0	65.0	56.0
mFe-Si	8.0	39.0	62.0	81.0
mFe-Si+P	15.6	59.0	64.0	71.0
hFe-C	47.0	77.0	65.0	50.0
hFe-P	7.0	34.0	65.0	22.0
hFe-Si	23.0	75.0	70.0	71.0
hFe-Si+P	11.5	66.0	76.0	53.0

Fe concentrations: Fe Conc.; no Fe: nFe; medium Fe: mFe; High Fe: hFe; control: C; phosphate:

P; silicic acid: Si.

57

58 Table 2 The significant effects of different treatments on arsenate (As(V)) mobilization in each
 59 sampling time, showing the significant effects of different treatments on arsenate release in the
 60 soil solution.

Treatments	Time			
	24	72	168	336
nFe-C	abc	abc	abc	abc
nFe-P	b*	b*	abc	bc*
nFe-Si	bc*, **	bc*, **	b*	abc
nFe-Si+P	abc	abc	cb**	abc
mFe-C	abc	abc	abc	abc
mFe-P	abc	abc	abc	abc
mFe-Si	abc	abc	abc	abc
mFe-Si+P	abc	abc	abc	abc
hFe-C	a*	a*	a*, **	a*, **
hFe-P	abc	abc	abc	bc**
hFe-Si	ac**	ac**	abc	abc
hFe-Si+P	abc	abc	abc	abc

61 Treatments followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Control: C;
 62 phosphate: P; silicic acid: Si. The significant difference between treatments at each sampling
 63 time is distinguished by the same star and color.

64 Table 3 The significant effects of different treatments on arsenite (As(III)) mobilization in each
 65 sampling time, showing the significant effects of different treatments on arsenite release in the
 66 soil solution.

Treatments	Time			
	24	72	168	336
nFe-C	bd [*] , ^{**}	a [*]	a [*]	ab
nFe-P	ab ^{**}	ab	ab	ab
nFe-Si	abc	ab	ab	ab
nFe-Si+P	abc	ab	ab	ab
mFe-C	cd [*]	a [*]	a [*]	ab
mFe-P	a [*]	ab	a	ab
mFe-Si	abc	ab	ab	b [*]
mFe-Si+P	abc	ab	ab	ab
hFe-C	abc	b [*]	b [*]	a [*]
hFe-P	ab ^{**}	b [*]	ab	a [*]
hFe-Si	abc	ab	ab	ab
hFe-Si+P	abc	ab	ab	ab

67 Treatments followed by the same letter are not significantly different (p<0.05). Control: C;
 68 phosphate: P; silicic acid: Si. The significant difference between treatments at each sampling time
 69 is distinguished by the same star and color.

70

71 References

- 72 1. Sander, R. Compilation of Henry's Law Constants for Inorganic and Organic Species of Potential
73 Importance in Environmental Chemistry. Max-Planck Institute of Chemistry, **1999**
- 74 2. Achtnich, C.; Bak, F. & Conrad, R. Competition for electron-donors among nitrate reducers,
75 ferric iron reducers, sulfate reducers, and methanogens in anoxic paddy soil. *Biol Fertil Soils*,
76 **1995**, 19, 65-72.
- 77 3. Mladenov, N.; Zheng, Y.; Miller, M. P.; Nemergut, D. R.; Legg, T.; Simone, B.; Hageman, C.;
78 Rahman, M. M.; Ahmed, K. M. and McKnight, D. M. Dissolved organic matter sources and
79 consequences for iron and arsenic mobilization in Bangladesh aquifers. *Environ. Sci. Technol.*
80 **2010**, 44, 123–128.
- 81 4. Conrad, R. Contribution of hydrogen to methane production and control of hydrogen
82 concentrations in methanogenic soils and sediments. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **1999** 28, 193-202.
- 83 5. Gao, C.; Sander, M.; Agethen, S. & Knorr, K-H. Electron accepting capacity of dissolved and
84 particulate organic matter control CO₂ and CH₄ formation in peat soils. *Geochim. Cosmochim.*
85 *Acta.* **2019**, 245, 266-277.

86